

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXXVI. Synthesis of Thiopegan Derivatives containing Basic Chains

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Some angular and linear thiopegans containing basic chains at position 4 have been synthesised by the condensation of various 2-aminobenzylideneamines with ω -thiocyanoketones, 2-chlorothiazoles, and allyl isothiocyanate.

Introduction of basic groups like =NH at position 4 in the angular¹ as well as linear² thiopegans, containing a thiazoline moiety, and substituted amino groups in the linear thiopegans, containing a thiazolidene moiety³, have been found to increase their antibacterial activity. The syntheses of some angular (I) as well as linear (II) thiopegans containing substituted amino groups at position 4 and a thiazoline moiety are reported herein:

Some 4-anilino-9,10-thiopega-2,10-diene (I:R.'=Ph) have been synthesised by the condensation of various ω -thiocyanoketones and 2-aminobenzylidene-aniline hydrochloride⁴. The latter being hygroscopic could not be isolated but was prepared *in situ* by treating 2-aminobenzylidene-aniline with dry HCl gas in anhydrous ethanolic solution. These products were isolated as dihydrochlorides (Table I)

TABLE I
Synthesis of 4-anilino-9,10-thiopega-2,10-diene Dihydrochlorides (I:R.'=Ph)

Ketone used.	Product formed. (R).	Yield.	**M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
ω -Th	-Ph	60%	270°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	C: 61.81% H: 4.24	61.88% 4.41
<i>p</i> -Bromo- ω -Th	C ₆ H ₄ Br (<i>p</i>)	40	230°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ BrCl ₂ S	N: 8.63	8.08
<i>p</i> -Chloro- ω -Th	C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>)	60	300°	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	N: 9.30	9.03

* ω -Th denotes ω -thiocyano-acetophenone

** Crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

1. Sandhev and Balhan, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19C, 109.
2. Balhan, Ph. D. thesis, Punjab University, 1961.
3. Narang, *et al.*, unpublished work.
4. Sharma *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 17, 53.

In the linear thiopegens(II), methylenedioxy group has been introduced in the benzene ring. 2-Amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene-*n*-butylamine (III: R'=(CH₂)₃CH₃), *p*-chloroaniline (III: R'=-C₆H₄Cl-*p*), and aniline (III: R'=Ph), obtained by the condensation of 6-aminopiperonal with *n*-butylamine, *p*-chloroaniline, and aniline respectively, were condensed with various 2-chlorothiazoles in presence of HCl and in phenol-melt solution⁵. The products were again isolated as dihydrochlorides (Table II).

TABLE II

Synthesis of 3,4-disubstituted 10,11-thiopega-2,9-diene Dihydrochloride (II)

2-Chloro-thiazole used	Product Formed R'	R	*M.P.	Formula	Found	Reqd.
4-(4'-bromophenyl)-T	-(CH ₂) ₃ CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₄ Br(<i>p</i>)	236°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ BrCl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	C: 47.71% H: 4.07 N: 8.22	47.27% 4.17 8.00
4-(4'-chlorophenyl)-T	..	-C ₆ H ₄ Cl(<i>p</i>)	238°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	C: 52.38 H: 4.61 N: 8.38	51.88 4.62 8.63
4-(4'-bromophenyl)-T	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₄ Br(<i>p</i>)	210°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ BrCl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	N: 7.53	7.82
4-(4'-methyl-phenyl)-T	-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl(<i>p</i>)	-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	202°	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	N: 9.45	9.10
4-phenyl-T	..	-C ₆ H ₅	182°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	N: 8.15	8.30
4-(4'-chloro-phenyl)-T	..	-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl(<i>p</i>)	195°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ Cl ₄ N ₃ O ₂ S	N: 8.25	7.76
4-(4'-bromophenyl)-T	..	-C ₆ H ₄ -Br(<i>p</i>)	180°	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ BrCl ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	N: 8.90	8.65

T denotes thiazole.

*Crystallized from glacial acetic acid.

The hydrochloride of [III: R'=(CH₂)₃CH₃] was prepared by saturating its ethereal solution with dry HCl gas, but it could not be isolated due to its hygroscopicity and was used as such after evaporation of ether. As the hydrochlorides of [III: R'=-C₆H₄-Cl-*p*; R'=Ph] could not be procured so for their condensations a few drops of fuming HCl were added in the reaction mixtures.

2-Methyl-4-*n*-butylamino-6,7-methylenedioxy-10,11-thiopega-9-ene [IV: R' = (CH₂)₃CH₃] as its trihydrochloride has been procured by the cyclisation of 3-allyl 4-butylamino-6,7-methylenedioxy-tetrahydroquinazoline-2-thiol [V: R' = (CH₂)₃CH₃] with HCl. Compound V: R' (CH₂)₃CH₃) was obtained by the condensation of [III: R' = (CH₂)₃CH₃] with allyl isothiocyanate².

Compound (V) was found to be active against Flexner at 1:5000 dilution, whereas (IV) was bacteriostatic in 1:1000 dilution.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Anilino-9,10-thiopega-2,10-diene Dihydrochlorides (I: R' = Ph)

To an ethanolic solution of 2-aminobenzylidene-aniline⁶, saturated with dry HCl gas, was added an equivalent amount of the appropriate *w*-thiocyanacetophenone. The mixture was refluxed for 5-6 hrs. Some solid separated during heating. The solvent was removed by distillation and the residue obtained in each case was purified.

2-Amino-4,5-methylenedioxy benzylidene-*n*-butylamine [III, R' = (CH₂)₃CH₃].—A mixture of 6-aminopiperonal (6.0 g) and *n*-butylamine was heated in a water bath. The reaction mixture melted but solidified after about one hour's heating. It was heated for 2-3 hrs. more. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished yellow needles, m.p. 159°, yield 3.9 g. 66°. (Found: N, 13.2. C₁₈H₁₈O₂N₂ requires N, 12.72%)

Its hydrochloride was prepared by passing dry HCl gas in its ethereal solution and was used after evaporating ether.

2-Amino-4,5-methylenedioxybenzylidene-*p*-chloroaniline (III: R' = C₆H₄Cl-*p*) and aniline (III: R' = Ph) were obtained by the condensation of equivalent amounts of 6-aminopiperonal with *p*-chloroaniline and aniline respectively.

Compound (III: R = C₆H₄Cl) was crystallised from ethanol as brown needles m.p. 165°. (Found: N, 10.63. C₁₄H₁₁N₂O₂ Cl requires N, 10.22%)

*Analyses are by Mr. B. N. Anand of the Panjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh, 6. Bulletin, Vol. 14, p. 24.

Compound (III: R=Ph) was crystallised from ethanol as yellow prisms, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 12.06. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.66%)

4—*Substituted Amino-8,7-methylenedioxy-10,11-thiopega-2,9-diene Dihydrochlorides* (IV: R' = $-(CH_2)_3CH_3$, $-C_6H_4Cl$, $-C_6H_5$). A mixture of equivalent amounts of appropriate 2-chlorothiazole and (III: R' = $p-C_6H_4Cl$ or Ph) in presence of a few drops of fuming HCl, or the hydrochloride of [III: R' = $(CH_2)_3CH_3$] was taken in a phenol-melt and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath at 130-40° for 4-5 hrs. with occasional stirring. It was cooled and diluted with anhydrous ether to remove phenol. The dark coloured residues thus obtained were purified.

2—*Thio-3-allyl-4-n-butylamino-6,7-methylenedioxytetrahydroquinazoline* (V):— A mixture of equivalent amounts of [III: R' = $(CH_2)_3CH_3$] and allyl isothiocyanate was heated on a water bath. After heating for 15 min. the mixture became mobile but solidified again after about an hour. It was heated for another 2-3 hrs. and the product was purified. The lower-melting, ethanol-soluble portion could not be identified. The ethanol-insoluble portion was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 254°. (Found: N, 13.6; S, 10.25 $C_{16}H_{21}O_2N_2S$ requires, N, 13.16; S, 10.03%).

2—*Methyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-4-n-butylamino-10:11-thiopega-9-ene Trihydrochloride* (IV):— Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of the quinazoline (V) (3.0 g) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) for 5-6 hrs. A yellow product separating during heating was cooled and crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 230°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 50.23; H, 5.96; N, 9.40. $C_{16}H_{24}N_3O_2Cl_3S$ requires C, 50.76; H, 6.10; N, 9.83%)